

DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL MARKETING THE FORMATION OF THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS THROUGH THE DISCIPLINE CONCEPT

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Abstract: *This article discusses the formation of the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of digital marketing through the concept of digitalization, in particular, the concept of digital business models and the digital market ecosystem.*

Keywords: *digital economy, start-up, business model, cost, digital market, Internet store, Business Model Canvas, digital platform, digital ecosystem, basic transaction.*

At the end of 2019, the COVID-19 pandemic caused turbulence in the entire world economy, leading to a single "start" state, regardless of the size of entrepreneurs. The problem they faced was almost the same for everyone. And it was in this case that marketing technology provided the greatest solution, requiring the use of the Internet and digital tools. Indeed, the digital economy and the digitalization requirements of its sectors of the economy form the basis of the business model of the modern economy.

The term "digital economy" was first coined in 1995 by American computer scientist Nicholas Negroponte. It includes the formation of the basic structure of technology companies, start-up projects in the digital economy, ie the technological aspects of projects[1]. Here, the first business model marketing has two main points of view: the first is the "cost" formed for customers; second, the approaches to cost formation in the internal system are taken into account.

In 1998, Paul Timmers supplemented the digital business model with conceptual comments such as "product architecture and data flow," "potential benefits for various businesses," and "source of revenue." The following digital market types of e-commerce were also included in the study: Internet-shop, e-commerce, Internet-auction, e-mail, marketplace (platform), social networks, integrators, thematic platforms (content platform), information broker, etc[2].

The Business Model Canvas, proposed by Alexander Ostervelder in 2009, divides the canvas business model into two components, the revenue and expense block (Figure 1).

Leading partners	Leading types of activities	Valuable suggestions	Customer interaction	Consumer segments
	Management resources		Sales channel	
Cost structure		Income-generating flows		

Figure 1. Alexander Ostervelder's concept of a digital business model [3].

The business model developed by Lars Schwartz has created a value-creating chain, a mechanism that reflects competitiveness and market superiority, sources of income, through which he has developed digital “integrator”, “market maker” and “conductor” models in entrepreneurship. (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Lars Schwartz's concept of a digital business model [4].

Models developed by Oliver Gasman, Caroline Frankenberger, Mikaela Shiklar are the main marketing mechanisms of today's market, which include: target customers, valuable offers, value chain, profit mechanisms[5].

Indeed, while any digital models have taken into account the interests of market participants in the first place, little attention has been paid to the interactions that ensure the effectiveness of key players in the digital market. Based on the general aspects of the above models, we consider it important to distinguish the single ecosystem concept of any digital market (Figure 3).

Figure 3 A concept that ensures the interdependence of participants in a digital market ecosystem[6].

Data exchange can also be one of the leading influencing or complex influencing elements. At the same time, it determines the "unit of value" in decision-making on the exchange of information. It can be inside or outside the platform. We

believe that the correct definition of this situation depends on the "platform transaction", ie the term "basic transaction" proposed by Alex Mozaed and Nicholas Johnson, in which the criteria of formation, interaction, consumption, incentives lead. In our opinion, it is important to pay special attention to such criteria as "platform transaction", such as audience engagement, coordination, offering tools and services, setting procedures and standards.

The "platform transaction" in turn provides the "value" of the digital ecosystem and, as a result, forms an "alliance" of platform participants and visitors.

Through the concept and "value" of the digital market ecosystem, it will be relatively easy to develop strategic approaches and penetration strategies for digital platforms. There are a number of approaches to choose from, such as: creating personal values, creating a platform for a group of audiences only, synchronous adaptation. However, we believe that any digital platform should, first of all, maintain the openness of the market and the "union" of consumers.

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